

OPTIMIZATION OF MANDREL COVERAGE FOR COMPLEX SHAPE STRUCTURES MADE BY FILAMENT WINDING TECHNOLOGY

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ABSTRACT

Due to its nature, filament winding technology lends itself to automation using a CAD-CAM system. Until now filament winding technology has been used exclusively for manufacturing axi-symmetrical structures. Recently many efforts have been made to develop a mathematical model for the description of the slippage troubles that can occur during filament winding of complex shape components. This research work has led to the realization of a software package able to simulate the filament winding process, generate the winding paths and to predict the stability of the winding. However, in the application of filament winding to general shape composites, many problems concerning global coverage of the mandrel and stability control of the fibers can occur. The aim of this paper is to illustrate the model and the numerical methods by which the above mentioned problem has been solved.

Keywords: Filament Winding, Winding Simulation, Coverage, Stable Trajectory.

1. INTRODUCTION

Generally many non axi-symmetrical filament wound structures are obtained by cutting off those parts utilized for the filament return, after the artifact has been cured. An optimized process for these filament wound structures should reduce both primary material wastage and manufacture time. In order to achieve this goal, both coverage of the mandrel and the feed eye deposition trajectory have been optimized. The mathematical models and the relative software package have been developed, and experimental tests have been performed to validate the numerical code results.

2. THE GENERALIZED SLIPPAGE TENDENCY EQUATION

Given the parametric equations of the surface S in cylindrical coordinates (Fig. 1):

$$\begin{cases} x = r(z, \theta) \cdot \cos(\theta) \\ y = r(z, \theta) \cdot \sin(\theta) \\ z = z \end{cases}$$

and the parametric equations of the line Γ upon S :

$$\begin{cases} x = x(z, \theta(z)) = a(z) \\ y = y(z, \theta(z)) = b(z) \\ z = z = c(z) \end{cases}$$

Figure 1 - General filament winding geometry

the generalized slippage tendency equation is in the form [3]:

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dz} = \frac{\sqrt{(q_1 + q_4 \cdot \sin \alpha \cdot \cos \alpha) \cdot (q_1 \cdot \sin^2 \alpha + q_2 \cdot \sin \alpha \cdot \cos \alpha + q_3 \cdot \cos^2 \alpha)} \cdot K}{p_1 \cdot \cos \alpha} + \frac{-p_2 \cdot \sin^3 \alpha - p_3 \cdot \sin^2 \alpha \cdot \cos \alpha - p_4 \cdot \sin \alpha \cdot \cos^2 \alpha - p_5 \cdot \cos^3 \alpha}{p_1 \cdot \cos \alpha} \quad (1)$$

where the coefficients p and q are functions of the differential properties of the surface:

$$\begin{aligned} q_1 &= f(\rho_z) \\ q_2 &= f(\rho, \rho_z, \rho_\theta, \rho_{z\theta}) \\ q_3 &= f(\rho, \rho_{zz}) \\ q_4 &= f(\rho, \rho_z, \rho_{z\theta}) \\ p_1 &= f(\rho, \rho_z, \rho_\theta) \\ p_2 &= f(\rho, \rho_z, \rho_\theta) \\ p_3 &= f(\rho, \rho_z, \rho_\theta, \rho_{z\theta}) \\ p_4 &= f(\rho, \rho_z, \rho_\theta, \rho_{z\theta}, \rho_{zz}) \\ p_5 &= f(\rho_\theta, \rho_{zz}) \end{aligned}$$

The equation (1), together with

$$\frac{d\theta}{dz} = \frac{\sqrt{1 + \rho_z^2}}{\sqrt{\rho^2 + \rho_\theta^2}} \cdot \tan \alpha \quad (2)$$

constitute a set of first order ordinary differential equations that represent the stable trajectory of the fiber on the mandrel for each value of the slippage tendency $K \leq \mu$ (friction coefficient between the fiber and the mandrel). For correct analysis it is important to have accurate experimental values of μ for different kinds of fiber and matrix.

3. MANDREL COVERAGE OPTIMIZATION

After a finite element analysis, the winding angles are used as inputs to run the winding programme simulation. In some cases (such as vessels) the input data for a simulation programme also concern the domes, making the verification of trajectory stability the only necessary job. In other cases, only the winding angles in the useful zone are assigned, and here the simulation programme must verify the stability of the fibers to assure complete coverage of the mandrel. To obtain complete mandrel coverage each stable trajectory must lie alongside the previous one in the effective part of the structure. This is obtained for an axi-symmetrical shape by repeating the same trajectory after a simple rotation $\delta\theta = b/(\rho \cdot \cos(\alpha))$ (Fig. 2) of the mandrel for each end course of the winding machine carriage. For a non axi-symmetrical shape, it is possible to return the filament to an axi-symmetrical area, as in the above case, calculating a new trajectory in the effective area to align it alongside the previous one (Fig. 2). However, if one wants to reduce primary material wastage, it is necessary that the filament return

takes place in non axis-symmetrical zones of the mandrel; consequently the return procedure calculation is different. The problem is then to find the stable trajectory that allows such a return by solution of sets (1) and (2); this trajectory should depart from point (z_0, θ_1, ρ_1) and arrive at point (z_0, θ_2, ρ_2) thus consenting fiber alignment (Fig. 3). Because each trajectory is different from the previous it is necessary to repeat this procedure for each winding. To solve this problem we utilize the shooting method [4].

Figure 2 - Non axisymmetrical shape with filament return in a cylindrical part of the mandrel.

Figure 3 - Non axisymmetrical shape with filament return in a non-axisymmetrical part of the mandrel.

3.1. Application of the shooting method

Given a set of N differential equations :

$$\frac{dy_i(x)}{dx} = g_i(x, y_1, y_2, \dots, y_N) \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, N \quad (3)$$

with n_1 conditions at the point x_1

$$B_{1j}(x_1, y_1, y_2, \dots, y_N) = 0 \quad j = 1, \dots, n_1$$

and $n_2 = N - n_1$ at the point x_2

$$B_{2k}(x_2, y_1, y_2, \dots, y_N) = 0 \quad k = 1, \dots, n_2 \quad (4)$$

the shooting method assigns all N conditions at x_1 , solves the set (3) and corrects the n_2 freely specifiable starting value with a multidimensional Newton-Raphson method until the conditions (4) are satisfied. In fact, given an arbitrary vector V of dimension n_2 , a set of starting values y can be found as follows :

$$y_i(x_1) = y_i(x_1, V_1, V_2, \dots, V_{n_2}) \quad i = 1, \dots, N$$

At x_2 we define a discrepancy vector F , also of dimension n_2 , whose components measure how far we are from satisfying the n_2 boundary conditions at x_2 :

$$F_k = B_{2k}(x_2, y_1, y_2, \dots, y_N) = 0 \quad k = 1, \dots, n_2$$

Now we can find a vector value of V which zeroes the vector value of F , which means mathematically solving a set of n_2 linear equations:

$$[\alpha] \cdot \delta V = -F$$

and adding the correction back

$$V_{new} = V_{old} + \delta V$$

where

$$[\alpha]_{ij} = \frac{\delta F_i}{\delta V_j}$$

with

$$\frac{\delta F_i}{\delta V_j} \approx \frac{F_i(V_1, \dots, V_j + \Delta V_j, \dots) - F_i(V_1, \dots, V_j, \dots)}{\Delta V_j}$$

In our case the problem is the following:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{d\alpha}{dz} = \frac{\sqrt{(q_1 + q_4 \cdot \sin \alpha \cdot \cos \alpha)} \cdot (q_1 \cdot \sin^2 \alpha + q_2 \cdot \sin \alpha \cdot \cos \alpha + q_3 \cdot \cos^2 \alpha) \cdot K}{-p_2 \cdot \sin^3 \alpha - p_3 \cdot \sin^2 \alpha \cdot \cos \alpha - p_4 \cdot \sin \alpha \cdot \cos^2 \alpha - p_5 \cdot \cos^3 \alpha} + \frac{p_1 \cdot \cos \alpha}{p_1 \cdot \cos \alpha} \\ \frac{d\theta}{dz} = \frac{\sqrt{1 + \rho_z^2}}{\sqrt{\rho^2 + \rho_\theta^2}} \cdot \tan \alpha \\ \frac{dK}{dz} = 0 \end{array} \right. \quad (5)$$

Because the solution has a singular point for $\alpha = 90^\circ$ (filament return), it may be found by starting from both sides of the interval and trying to match continuity conditions at the point in question. Firstly, we integrate from $z = z_1$ to $z = z_f$ and secondly from $z = z_2$ to $z = z_f$ with these conditions:

$$z = z_1 \Rightarrow \begin{cases} \alpha = \alpha_1 \\ \theta = \theta_1 \end{cases}$$

$$z = z_2 \Rightarrow \begin{cases} \alpha = \alpha_2 \\ \theta = \theta_2 \end{cases}$$

$$z = z_f \Rightarrow \alpha = 90^\circ$$

The solution is found so that the slippage tendency $K \leq \mu$. The range of singular points ($z = z_f$) is determined by starting from both sides with two values of K (min = 0, max = μ). We iteratively change the point $z = z_f$ in this range, until the solution of the set (5) converges. The angle θ_2 which consents fiber alignment can be determined by:

$$\theta_2 = \theta_{old} + \delta\theta \quad (6)$$

with $\delta\theta$ (Fig. 3) as the abscissa which zeroes the function:

$$f_{\delta\theta} = \frac{b}{\cos \alpha} - \frac{1}{12} [6 \cdot \delta\theta \cdot (\rho_p + \rho_n) + \delta\theta^2 \cdot (\rho_{\theta_p} + \rho_{\theta_n})] \quad (7)$$

where ρ_p and ρ_{θ_p} are calculated at the midpoint of the previously wound fiber and ρ_n and ρ_{θ_n} are determined at each iteration from an interpolation bicubic splines modulus. The second part of the function (7) is determined by solving

$$\int_{\theta_p}^{\theta_n} \rho(\theta) \cdot d\theta$$

where, for the kind of interpolation used:

$$\rho(u) = \rho_p \cdot F_0(u) + \rho_n \cdot F_1(u) + \frac{d\rho_p}{du} \cdot G_0(u) + \frac{d\rho_n}{du} \cdot G_1(u) \quad (8)$$

with

$$u = \frac{\theta - \theta_p}{\theta_n - \theta_p}$$

and F are Hermite basic functions.

By using this method, it is possible (in cases of sufficient friction coefficient) to ensure filament return in a generic part of the mandrel. This means a significant reduction in material wastage. In Fig. 4 the two different methods are compared.

Figure 4 - Numerical simulation of coverage of the same shape component where filament return takes place in different areas

4. EXPERIMENTAL

This phase is necessary to check the code. The code consists of two basic modules. The first allows calculation of the winding trajectory to obtain complete coverage of the mandrel, while the second, which continues on the basis of the output from the first programme, determines the correct trajectory of feed eye deposition so that both the physical and kinetic limits of the winding machine axes are satisfied. Generally, for large winding machines (such as those utilized to product eolic blades), the rotational axis is that which bears the greater dynamic load. To alleviate this problem the trend of the rotational angle θ_e with time must be smooth. This is obtained by ensuring that the angle between the plane tangent for the point of deposition on the mandrel and the horizontal plane is constant. The physical limits are respected by minimizing the distance between the deposition feed eye and the mandrel surface. A suitable routine optimizes the speed of the axes by using a cubic spline interpolation. The winding machine utilized for the test has four axes (translation of the carriage along x, y, z and rotation θ_e of the mandrel). The results of the numerical simulation and the experimental tests are shown in Fig 5.

Figure 5 - Comparison between winding numerical simulation and experimental mandrel coverage.

Here some points where the mandrel is not perfectly covered are visible. This is due to the small friction coefficient between the utilized fibers (dry kevlar) and the mandrel.

5. CONCLUSION

This paper describes a design philosophy appropriate to advanced filament winding technology. The experimental tests agree well with the numerical simulation results.

The code can be interfaced with a finite element programme, constituting a complete package for the lay-down phase of filament winding technology. Seeing as the finite element programme is based on the classical lamination theory, because filament wound structures contain cross-over points it is necessary to take their influence into account during stress analysis. This last will be one of our research areas in the near future.

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